

Review

Mechanically induced long-period gratings via metal wire winding

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ABSTRACT

A fully mechanical approach for producing long-period gratings (LPGs) by helically winding a thin metallic wire around an optical fiber is investigated. A dedicated setup enables precise control of the winding period and real-time spectral monitoring during fabrication. Scanning electron microscopy confirms uniform wire–fiber contact and well-defined periodicity. Clear and repeatable LPG spectral responses are obtained for winding periods between 400 and 600 μm , while shorter periods (200–300 μm) fail due to mechanical and geometric constraints, defining a practical fabrication window. The resonance wavelength and coupling strength are independently controlled by the winding period and number of turns. Refractive-index sensitivity is demonstrated, indicating sensing potential.

1. Introduction

Long-period gratings (LPGs) are widely used photonic components that enable controlled coupling between the guided core mode and forward-propagating cladding modes through a periodic perturbation of the refractive index along an optical fiber [1]. This coupling is governed by a phase-matching condition, resulting in distinct attenuation bands in the transmission spectrum whose positions depend on the grating period, wavelength, and surrounding refractive index. Owing to these properties, LPGs have been extensively employed in optical communications for applications such as optical filtering [2], mode conversion [3], gain flattening in optical amplifiers [4], and dispersion or loss control. Additionally, their sensitivity to external perturbations has made them highly attractive for sensing applications, including temperature, strain, and refractive index sensing [5,6].

Nowadays, there is a wide range of methods that have been developed to produce LPGs, which can be broadly classified into optical, thermal, and mechanical approaches. Optical inscription methods, such as UV inscription [7], CO₂ laser irradiation [8] and femtosecond laser processing [9], are capable of producing high-quality and permanent gratings with well-defined spectral characteristics. However, these techniques typically require expensive, specialized equipment and strict material compatibility. Thermal and electric-based methods, including electric arc discharge [10], offer a more accessible alternative but still impose limitations on repeatability and process control. In contrast, mechanically induced LPGs—based on periodic deformation of the fiber through techniques such as microbending or pressure-induced

modulation [11,12], provide a simple, low-cost, and inherently reconfigurable approach. Nevertheless, existing mechanical methods often rely on fixed or pre-fabricated periodic structures, limiting their flexibility, and generally lack the ability to monitor the grating formation process in real time. provide a simple, low-cost, and inherently reconfigurable approach. Nevertheless, existing mechanical methods often rely on fixed or pre-fabricated periodic structures, limiting their flexibility, and generally lack the ability to monitor the grating formation process in real time [13]. These limitations encourage the investigation of alternative fabrication techniques that can directly apply a tunable, periodic perturbation to the fiber while enabling real-time monitoring of the grating's spectral growth. In addition to increasing the variety of low-cost prototyping techniques, a mechanically controlled method that establishes the grating period, the number of applied perturbations, and the stress profile during fabrication can offer important insights into LPG formation mechanisms [14]. In this work, we investigate a fully mechanical technique to produce LPGs by periodically winding a metallic wire around a standard optical fiber. The proposed approach enables precise control of the grating periodicity and the number of imposed perturbations, while simultaneously allowing real-time acquisition of the transmission spectrum during the winding process. A systematic study is performed over a wide range of mechanical periods to evaluate the formation and spectral response of the induced gratings. Additionally, the method is assessed in terms of geometric accuracy and the influence of the number of imposed periods on grating formation. Overall, this work aims to elucidate the fundamental capabilities and practical constraints of mechanically induced LPGs as a simple and

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equipment-free approach for fabricating fiber-optic gratings.

2. Working principle

LPGs allow coupling between the fundamental core mode and forward-propagating cladding modes by periodically modulating the effective refractive index along the fiber axis. The phase-matching condition, which is dependent on the grating period Λ and the effective indices of the interacting modes, determines the resonance wavelength (λ_{res}) for which this coupling occurs, and is expressed by:

$$\lambda_{res} = \Lambda (n_{co} - n_{cl,m}) \quad (1)$$

where n_{co} is the effective refractive index of the fundamental core mode and $n_{cl,m}$ is the effective index of the m^{th} cladding mode. A predictable spectral response requires precise mechanical control of the winding pitch because Eq. (1) demonstrates that the resonance wavelength shifts linearly with the imposed period Λ .

A periodic stress field is created along the fiber when the wire is tightly wound around it, and longitudinal tension is applied to keep it in contact. Through the photoelastic effect, this stress modifies the local refractive index [15]. The change in the index perturbation, Δn_i , in a stressed area, is expressed by Eq. (2):

$$\Delta n_i = - n_0 p_e \varepsilon_i \quad (2)$$

where n_0 is the unperturbed refractive index, p_e is the effective photoelastic constant of the fiber and ε_i is the strain induced by the contact force of the wire. The areas beneath the wire in the mechanical configuration under study experience higher localized stress, whereas the areas between wire turns are essentially unstressed, as shown in Fig. 1. The LPG is made up of this recurring change in refractive index.

Unlike conventional pressure-induced LPGs, in which pressure is applied perpendicular to the fiber propagation axis, the LPG presented in Fig. 1 features an angle introduced during the winding process, creating a helical pressure that modulates the refractive index along a helical path, thereby coupling more complex modes. In other words, wrapping the wire along the fiber breaks the symmetry of the structure by introducing an azimuthal component into the perturbation, adding both axial and transverse components, and enabling the coupling of specific modes, including modes with azimuthal dependence. This type of grating is commonly referred to in literature as helical LPGs [16,17].

The standard coupled-mode formulation can be used to describe the transmission spectrum of an LPG, where the ac coupling coefficient κ and the grating length l determine the power transfer from the core mode to a cladding mode [18]. The normalized transmission at resonance is obtained by assuming uniform coupling and ignoring loss, and follows as in Eq. (3):

$$T = \cos^2(\kappa_{co-cl}^{ac} l) \quad (3)$$

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the mechanical method, showing a wire around the fiber with pitch $\Lambda = 600\mu\text{m}$.

which emphasizes that the magnitude of the induced refractive-index modulation controls the depth of the attenuation dips. Because each wire turn adds a new periodic perturbation, the dip depth changes as more turns are added. This makes it possible to observe the grating growth in real time simply by monitoring the transmission spectrum during fabrication.

3. Fabrication and characterization

The experimental setup used for winding an $80 \mu\text{m}$ metallic wire onto a standard single-mode fiber (Cabelte S.A.) is shown in Fig. 2. To ensure proper alignment and stability during the winding process, both ends of the fiber were secured with two fiber clamps labeled “3” in the figure. The metallic wire was initially wound around the fiber with three full turns, after which a UV-curable resin was applied to promote adhesion between the wire and the fiber. During winding, the wire exerts a tangential force on the fiber, generating a torque around its axis. Due to the limited gripping force of the fiber clamps, it was necessary to apply a small drop of UV-curable resin between the fiber and the clamp to prevent fiber slipping. To maintain axial tension on the fiber, one of the clamps was mounted on a micrometer translation stage, labeled as “6”. Once assembled, this stage was adjusted to slightly stretch the fiber, ensuring it remained taut before the winding process began.

To maintain constant tension on the metallic wire during the winding process, it was necessary to install a system that allowed controlled unwinding from the spool (component 2.3). For this purpose, a bearing (component 2.1) was used to ensure that the spool could rotate freely around an axis. Because the bearing did not match the spool's dimensions, a customized adapter was designed and later 3D-printed

Fig. 2. (a) Picture and (b) schematic of the implemented setup for the metal wire winding around the optical fiber: 1 – optical fiber; 2 – wrapping system; 3 – fiber clamps (the second is hidden behind “4”); 4 – rotational stage; 5 – linear translation stage; 6 – micrometer translation stage. In Visualization 1, the setup can be seen in operation.

(component 2.2). To ensure a constant tension in the metallic wire on the fiber, a compression spring (component 2.4) was incorporated into the assembly. The tension applied by the wire to the fiber was adjusted by displacing the optical post against the spring, thereby increasing or decreasing the friction on the spool's rotation and, consequently, providing more restricted or more free movement, respectively. The metallic wire passed through a hypodermic needle (component 2.5) with an internal diameter of approximately 500 μm . The tip of this needle was positioned close to the fiber to ensure precise placement of the wire during winding.

The fiber wrapping system, "2", is mounted on a rotational stage (Newport, URB100CC), allowing the wrapping of the metallic wire around the optical fiber. This positioner and its assembly are integrated into a motorized linear translation stage. (Newport, UTS150PP), enabling linear motion of the metallic wire along the optical fiber length. Both stages were controlled simultaneously through a universal motion controller (Newport, XPS), operated via a custom MATLAB® routine. The rotational stage operated at a constant angular velocity (V_R) of 65.5°/s, chosen to avoid excessive speeds that could compromise the mechanical stability of the coupled system during fabrication, while the linear positioner velocity (V_L) was adjusted to reach the desired winding period, such that $V_L = \Lambda \cdot V_R / 360$. To spectrally characterize the structures, the fiber used for winding was first spliced to two optical fiber pigtailed using a fusion splicer (Fujikura, FSM-60S). The gratings were interrogated in transmission during the fabrication process using a broadband source (Fianium WhiteLaser SC Series, WL-SC400-2) covering the 1200–1700 nm range. The transmitted signal was continuously monitored with an optical spectrum analyzer (OSA, Advantest Q8384) configured with a spectral resolution of 0.05 nm. Data acquisition was automated, enabling the collection of spectra at 5 spectra per minute.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Analysis by scanning electron microscopy and optical microscopy

In **Visualization 1**, the fabrication setup helically winding the metal wire onto the optical fiber. The fabrication was performed for winding periods ranging from 200 to 600 μm in increments of 100 μm . During the fabrication and characterization stages reported in this work, no structural damage, cracking, or fiber breakage was noticed.

The spatial distribution of the induced refractive index modulation is determined by the physical conformity of the metallic wire surrounding the fiber surface. To this end, the structure was observed under a scanning electron microscope (SEM) and in an optical microscope. It is important to note that when the winding process terminates, the wire stress must be maintained in the fiber. Thus, to remove the fiber structure from the setup, the final wire turn is secured to the fiber by applying a drop of photopolymerizable resin. An SEM image of the metallic wire wound around the fiber with a period of 600 μm is shown in Fig. 3.

From the image shown in Fig. 3, it is possible to observe that the metal wire follows a helical path along the principal axis of the fiber, having a well-defined spacing between turns. Furthermore, it is also possible to observe that the wire is always in close contact with the optical fiber. Based on these observations, we assume that the fundamental requirements for a periodic strain transfer from the wire to the fiber are met.

To assess the method's precision and accuracy, the winding period was measured over 50 turns for each periodic structure. To keep the measurement method simple, the measurements were made under an optical microscope (see the example image taken for a fiber wound with a 600 μm period Fig. 4a)). The results of this analysis are presented in Fig. 4b).

As observed in Fig. 4b), for smaller periods, especially at 200–300 μm , the analysis reveals a significant loss of geometrical accuracy, where the observed values deviate from the theoretical curve marked as red

Fig. 3. SEM image of the metallic wire helically wound around an optical fiber with a period of $\approx 600 \mu\text{m}$. It is possible to observe a well-defined periodic structure and a uniform contact between the wire and the fiber surface.

Fig. 4. Comparison of the nominal and measured periods for different target values, highlighting the smaller precision and accuracy at smaller winding periods.

Table 1
Precision of the fabrication for different helical periods.

Predicted Λ (μm)	200	300	400	500	600	700	800
Precision (%)	61.5	73.7	87.0	96.0	96.7	97.2	92.3

dashed line. Also, the winding precision is low (see Table 1), with values ranging from 60 to 70%. The result was due to the wire's lack of compliance at high curvatures. This inconsistent perturbation will lead to inefficient phase-matching coupling, as will be discussed later.

The diameter of the metallic wire is an important parameter in the proposed fabrication approach. For wires with a circular cross-section, such as the one used in this work, the effective duty cycle of the induced perturbation remains approximately constant, and thus only minor variations in the spectral response are expected. However, the wire diameter significantly influences the mechanical behavior during the winding process. In particular, larger diameters increase bending stiffness, which may limit conformity to small periods and affect fabrication precision, while thinner wires enable improved geometrical adaptability and mechanical stability. Therefore, the wire diameter primarily acts as a tuning parameter for fabrication conditions and achievable grating geometries.

4.2. Spectral characterization of the mechanically induced LPG

The first spectral characterization was made for the structure presented in Fig. 3, consisting of a periodic winding of 600 μm . The results for this characterization are displayed in Fig. 5a) for the different spectra acquired during the growth of the structures (increase in the number of turns/periods) and in Fig. 5b) for the spectra reached at exactly 29 turns.

Four transmission dips were observed in the infrared region during fabrication. They gradually increase their attenuation as the number of turns rises, illustrating the steady increase in coupling strength as more

periods are added. During grating growth, an apparent dip splitting was observed, particularly evident in the second resonance (Fig. 5a)). While dip splitting can arise from birefringence, the observed separation between resonances is significantly larger than typically expected. This suggests that the effect is more likely due to the simultaneous excitation of multiple cladding modes induced by the helical perturbation. At a specific number of turns, the strength of each attenuation band reaches its maximum and starts to decrease. Also, out-of-band losses start to increase as the number of periods increases, suggesting that mechanical deformation imposed by the wire on the optical fiber generates curvature-induced losses. In Fig. 5b), the spectrum obtained when the resonance band numbered as “2” reached its maximum coupling strength, namely at 29 periods, is shown.

To get additional information about the coupling dynamics, it was plotted in Fig. 6, the dip power attenuation of each resonance band, as a function of the number of wound periods.

According to Eq. (3), the transmission power exhibits sinusoidal behavior as a function of the coupling coefficient and the grating length. This performance is observed in Fig. 6, which shows a monotonic decrease in the dip power till reaching a maximum attenuation, which is then followed by a decline as coupling between the core mode and the specific cladding mode becomes weaker. The number of periods for which each spectral resonance reaches its maximum coupling strength is different and this analysis can be used to establish an endpoint criterion for a specific attenuation band during the fabrication.

To check the capability to reproduce the same grating results, we fabricated a new 600 μm LPG. The results reached for this grating and for the earlier ones are shown together in Fig. 7.

The number of periods needed to maximize the coupling efficiency for the 1st dip of the second LPG structure shown in Fig. 7 was 31 periods, which was slightly more than the earlier one, i.e., 29 periods. Despite the similar spectral signature, there is a slight wavelength shift difference between the gratings (i.e., ≈ 30 nm) and slightly different coupling strengths, showing that, despite similarities, there is still room for improvement.

The spectral characterization was also performed on structures with smaller winding periods. Despite repeated attempts, the spectra obtained for structures processed to reach periods of 200 and 300 μm didn't show any attenuation bands or signal degradation. These results were expected due to the lack of precision and accuracy reached for these winding periods, as confirmed through Fig. 4. In fact, for smaller periods, the fabrication process becomes increasingly sensitive to positioning accuracy, leading to geometrical deviations. Additionally,

Fig. 5. (a) Spectra growth during the periodic winding of a structure designed to have $\Lambda = 600 \mu\text{m}$. The arrows were added to make the growth over time easier to understand. (b) Spectrum reached for only 29 periods.

Fig. 6. Evolution of the dip power attenuation of each resonance band that appears in Fig. 5a) as a function of the number of wound periods.

Fig. 7. Spectra obtained for two mechanically induced LPGs with winding periods of 600 μm and a total of 29 and 31 periods.

shorter periods impose higher curvature on the metallic wire, increasing its bending strain and stored elastic energy. This results in reduced conformity to the fiber surface and may induce local relaxation or partial unwinding, ultimately degrading the uniformity of the induced perturbation. To mitigate these effects, the use of thinner wires can be advantageous, as their lower bending stiffness allows improved adaptation to high-curvature winding conditions and enhances fabrication precision for shorter periods. For winding periods equal to or above 400 μm , the structures were able to show attenuation bands with good coupling strength, as can be observed in Fig. 8.

The results presented in Fig. 8 were optimized to maximize the coupling strength of the first spectral dips in the transmission spectrum. These were reached for periods of 30, 35, and 29 for the gratings with periods of 400, 500 and 600 μm , respectively. The resonance location and dip strength indicate the combined effects of coupling efficiency and phase matching (which is period-dependent). These findings verify that functional LPGs with consistent spectral signatures in the 400-600 μm range can be produced using the suggested mechanical winding technique.

Long-term stability is an important consideration for the practical deployment of the proposed structures. Although a systematic study was not performed, the spectral response of the fabricated gratings remained

Fig. 8. Comparison of the transmission spectra obtained for mechanically induced LPGs with winding periods of $\Lambda = 400, 500$ and $600 \mu\text{m}$.

stable over a period of several months after fabrication, indicating good intrinsic stability of the structure. To assess the potential of the produced structures for sensing applications, an additional grating with a winding period of 600 μm was fabricated, and its spectrum was measured in air ($n = 1.000$) and in a sugar-water solution ($n = 1.4050$). The result can be seen in Fig. 9.

When the external refractive index is changed, a distinct spectral shift is seen; the largest displacement happens at the third attenuation band, where a wavelength shift of 3.88 nm is measured. Based on the observed wavelength shift and refractive index difference, an estimated sensitivity of approximately 9.6 nm/RIU can be inferred. This value is consistent with the lower end of the reported range for conventional LPGs operating outside optimized regimes. However, this result was intended to confirm the structure's sensing capability rather than to represent its maximum achievable performance. Despite this, the observed shift clearly confirms the proposed structure's capability to operate as a refractive index sensor.

5. Conclusion

This work demonstrates that helically winding a metallic wire around a standard optical fiber constitutes a viable and physically transparent approach for the mechanical induction of long-period gratings, provided that the winding period is within a well-defined operational range. By combining direct geometric inspection with real-time spectral monitoring, it was shown that winding periods

Fig. 9. Transmission spectra of a periodically wound fiber with $\Lambda = 600 \mu\text{m}$ measured in air ($n = 1.0000$) and a sugar-water solution ($n = 1.4050$), showing a wavelength shift of 3.88 nm at the third attenuation band.

between 400 and 600 μm enable uniform strain transfer, accurate periodicity, and efficient core-cladding mode coupling, while shorter periods fail to produce functional gratings due to cumulative mechanical and geometric constraints. Rather than representing a limitation of the method, this result clarifies the fundamental interplay between pitch accuracy, strain localization, and phase-matching requirements in mechanically induced LPGs. The ability to continuously tune both resonance wavelength and coupling strength during fabrication offers a distinctive advantage for rapid prototyping and for studying grating growth dynamics. Finally, the observed refractive-index sensitivity confirms that the proposed structures are suitable for sensing applications, positioning this technique not as an alternative to laser-based inscription methods, but as a simple, low-cost platform for controlled mechanical perturbation and fundamental studies of LPG formation.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Fábio Dias: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Investigation, Data curation. **João Preizal:** Validation, Supervision, Software, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Ricardo Oliveira:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.optlaseng.2026.109902](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optlaseng.2026.109902).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] Erdogan T. Fiber grating Spectra. *J Lightwave Technol* 1997;15(8):1277–94. <https://doi.org/10.1109/50.618322>.
- [2] Seraji FE, Farsinezhad S, Anzabi LC. Optimization of long-period grating inscribed in large mode area photonic crystal fiber for design of bandstop filter. *Optik (Stuttg)* 2011;122(1):58–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijleo.2010.02.004>.
- [3] Chen S, Ma Y, Su H, Fan X, Liu Y. Few-mode Fiber-based long-period Fiber gratings: a review. *J Opt Photonics Res* 2024;1(1):02–15. <https://doi.org/10.47852/bonviewjopr42022414>.
- [4] Singh R, Sunanda, Sharma EK. Gain flattening by long period gratings in erbium doped fibers. *Opt Commun* 2004;240(1–3):123–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optcom.2004.06.023>.
- [5] Bhatia V, Vengsarkar AM. Optical fiber long-period grating sensors. *Opt Lett* 1996; 21(9):692. <https://doi.org/10.1364/OL.21.000692>.
- [6] Kumar S, Mahakud R, Kumar J, Prakash O. Highly sensitive and thermally stable simultaneous sensing of surrounding refractive index and temperature using cascaded turnaround point LPG. *J Opt (India)* 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12596-025-02914-1>.
- [7] Guan B-O, Tam H-Y, Ho S-L, Liu S-Y, Dong X-Y. Growth of long-period gratings in H 2-loaded Fiber after 193-nm UV inscription. *IEEE Photonics Technol Lett* 2000;12 (6):642–4. <https://doi.org/10.1109/68.849070>.
- [8] Almeida T, Oliveira R, André P, Rocha A, Facão M, Nogueira R. Automated technique to inscribe reproducible long-period gratings using a CO₂ laser splicer. *Opt Lett* 2017;42(10):1994. <https://doi.org/10.1364/ol.42.001994>.
- [9] Li B, Jiang L, Wang S, Tsai HL, Xiao H. Femtosecond laser fabrication of long period fiber gratings and applications in refractive index sensing. *Opt Laser Technol* 2011; 43(8):1420–3. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optlastec.2011.04.011>.
- [10] Godbout N, Daxhelet X, Maurier A, Lacroix S. Long-period fiber grating by electrical discharge. In: 24th European Conference on Optical Communication. ECOC '98 (IEEE Cat. No.98TH8398). Telefunica; 1998. p. 397–8. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ECOC.1998.732616>.
- [11] Oliveira R, Sousa LM, Rocha AM, Nogueira R, Bilro L. UV inscription and pressure induced long-period gratings through 3d printed amplitude masks. *Sensors* 2021; 21(6):1977. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s21061977>.
- [12] Rego G. Long-period fiber gratings mechanically induced by winding a string around a fiber/grooved tube set. *Microw Opt Technol Lett* 2008;50(8):2064–8. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mop.23572>.
- [13] Valente NF, Bilro L, Oliveira R. 3D printing of long period gratings for curvature applications. *EPJ Web Conf* 2021;255:12001. <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/202125512001>.
- [14] Oliveira R, Nogueira R, Bilro L. 3D printed long period gratings and their applications as high sensitivity shear-strain and torsion sensors. *Opt Express* 2021; 29(12):17795. <https://doi.org/10.1364/oe.427387>.
- [15] Chaves RC, de A. P. Pohl A, Abe I, Sebem R, Paterno A. Strain and temperature characterization of LPGs written by CO₂ laser in pure silica LMA photonic crystal fibers. *Photonic Sens* 2015;5(3):241–50. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13320-015-0250-3>.
- [16] Ma C, Wang J, Yuan L. Review of helical long-period fiber gratings. *Photonics* 2021;8(6):193. <https://doi.org/10.3390/photonics8060193>.
- [17] Sheykhan A, Rocha AM, Oliveira R. Helical long-period grating through a commercial CO₂ laser fiber processing machine for torsion sensor applications. *IEEE Sens J* 2024;24(21):34481–6. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSEN.2024.3454351>.
- [18] James SW, Tatam RP. Optical fibre long-period grating sensors: characteristics and application. *Meas Sci Technol* 2003;14:R49–61. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0957-0233/14/5/201>.